

1 **Cigarette smoke enhances transformation by disrupting senescence-associated interferon**
2 **pathway activation.**

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7 Tobacco products including cigarettes are believed to function as carcinogens by acting as mutagens,
8 meaning cigarette smoke exposure results in accumulation of de novo mutation over time. We
9 demonstrate here that cigarette smoke possesses a strong interferon pathway neutralization effect which
10 corresponds to a senescence neutralizing property: exposure of human cells to cigarette smoke extract in
11 vitro resulted in transcriptome level perturbation of a full complement of interferon-stimulated genes
12 recently described as requisite component genes of the senescence program. Cigarette smoke
13 accelerates transformation by licensing senescence bypass through neutralization of the interferon genes
14 of the senescence program. Mutagenic properties of cigarette smoke are either overestimated or function
15 together with senescence evasion conferred by interferon neutralization.
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